

Drug Utilization Pattern of Analgesics in Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital (500-Bedded), Mingalardon

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Abstract

Background: Opioid and non-opioid analgesic drugs are commonly used for the management of pain and inflammation in orthopaedic patients.

Objective: The aim of this study is to determine the drug utilization pattern of opioid and non-opioid analgesics in Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital (500-bedded), Mingalardon.

Methods: This is a hospital-based cross-sectional descriptive study, carried out for a period of three months. In this study, the drug utilization pattern of opioid and non-opioid analgesics was analyzed by using the World Health Organization Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification (ATC)/Defined Daily Dose (DDD) methodology and drug utilization (DU) 90% segments.

Results: Total 278 patients were admitted during the study period, and 94% (260 patients) were prescribed analgesics. The highest representation in terms of age was within the 18-35 years, comprising 57.69% of the total. Gender distribution indicated that 81% were males while 19% were females. Out of the patients, 58.08% received non-opioid analgesics, 10.77% were prescribed opioid analgesics, and 31.15% received a combination of both. The utilization rate for opioid analgesics stood at 22.5 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. Among these, oral tramadol tablets were the most frequently administered at 18 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. In contrast, non-opioid analgesics exhibited a much higher utilization rate, reaching 99.74 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. Aceclofenac was the most commonly prescribed non-opioid analgesic at 35.67 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. The DU 90% segment included aceclofenac, diclofenac, paracetamol, tramadol tablets, meloxicam, and injection tramadol. Proton pump inhibitors were the most commonly prescribed gastroprotective agent, with 57.32% of the study population.

Conclusion: The study contributes to a better understanding of healthcare practices in specialized medical settings like a military hospital and emphasizes the use of analgesics in an orthopaedic hospital.

Keywords: drug utilization, analgesics, ATC classification, Defined Daily Dose (DDD), DU 90%

1. Introduction

Drug utilization research, as defined by the World Health Organization (WHO), encompasses the marketing, distribution, prescribing, and utilization of drugs within a society, with a keen focus on the resultant medical, social, and economic ramifications (1). They shed light on prescribing habits within specific therapeutic domains, aiding healthcare systems in comprehending, interpreting, and enhancing medication prescription, administration, and usage (2). Drug utilization research unveils multifaceted facets of drug use and prescription, including usage patterns, quality of utilization, determinants of use, and outcomes (3).

To quantify drug usage, a classification system and a unit of measurement are essential. Presently, drug utilization research employs the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system and the Defined Daily Dose (DDD) as recommended by WHO. The ATC classifies drugs into distinct groups based on their target organ or system, as well as their chemical, pharmacological, and therapeutic characteristics, across five hierarchical levels. The DDD serves as an assumed average daily maintenance dose for a drug's primary indication in adults and functions as a unit of measurement, not as a prescribed or actual dose (3).

The Drug Utilization 90% (DU90%) index stands as a straightforward, cost-effective, and adaptable technique for assessing the quality of drug prescriptions. It identifies drugs accounting for 90% of the total volume of prescribed medications by ranking them based on DDD (2). The remaining 10% may encompass specific drugs employed for rare conditions in patients with drug intolerance or adverse reactions, complex co-morbid conditions, or therapy prescribed by other clinicians (3).

Drug utilization studies are particularly insightful and informative when focused on frequently used therapeutic drugs such as antibiotics, analgesics, and chemotherapy, or those representing significant therapeutic advancements (4). Among these, analgesic drugs have been the subject of studies in various settings, hospitals, and countries (5, 6, 7).

The availability of many kinds of analgesics in the market raises concerns about irrational prescription practices. Continuous research endeavors are warranted to identify more effective and safer drug utilization patterns for analgesics in patients suffering from conditions such as post-operative pain, arthritic pain, and fractures (8). In Myanmar, various researchers have conducted drug utilization studies in diverse clinical settings. Aung (2013) investigated the drug utilization patterns of opioid and non-opioid analgesics in Yangon Orthopaedic Hospital, finding that aceclofenac was the most prescribed drug, with 25.89

DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. Notably, five drugs were included in the drug utilization 90% segment: aceclofenac (33.3%), etoricoxib (17.8%), paracetamol (17.4%), diclofenac (17.2%), and meloxicam (6.1%) (5). Despite these valuable insights, there remains a substantial need for further research on the drug utilization of opioid and non-opioid analgesics in various hospitals across Myanmar to optimize their use. Rigorous monitoring of analgesic consumption can aid in delineating diverse approaches to pain management. Furthermore, data from drug utilization studies may facilitate informed decisions regarding drug procurement for government and military hospitals. This drug utilization data holds the potential to inform the development of Myanmar's essential drug list and guide government authorities in shaping drug usage policies.

Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital (500-bedded), Mingalardon, stands as a tertiary center specializing in the treatment of orthopedic patients, including those admitted due to war injuries and other orthopedic conditions. Consequently, opioid and non-opioid analgesics are frequently prescribed to manage pain in patients at this hospital. However, there is an absence of previous data regarding analgesic utilization in military hospitals, including Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital. The Directorate of Medical Services of Myanmar Army is responsible for determining the pharmaceutical needs of military hospitals and procuring medications accordingly. Data on drug utilization in military hospitals could provide valuable insights to the Directorate of Medical Services for informed procurement decisions. The information gap in drug utilization data within military hospitals underscores the necessity for further research.

This descriptive cross-sectional study, conducted within the orthopedic wards of Defence Services Orthopedic Hospital (500-bedded), Mingalardon, seeks to address this information gap. The study aims to gather data on the clinical conditions for which opioid and non-opioid analgesics are prescribed, patient demographics for whom these drugs are prescribed, drug utilization 90% for both opioid and non-opioid analgesics, and concurrent usage of gastro-protective medications. The findings of this study can offer insights into the extent of opioid and non-opioid analgesic utilization and the most commonly prescribed drugs. Additionally, this research can provide feedback to prescribers regarding the overall use of these analgesic drugs at Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital (500-bedded), Mingalardon. The collected data can guide decisions regarding the supply of analgesic drugs in military hospitals, aiding in the optimization of pain management strategies.

2. Methods

A hospital-based cross-sectional descriptive study was done over three months, from May 1, 2019, to July 31, 2019. Data collection was done in Trauma ward, General Orthopedic ward, Family ward, and Officer ward of the Defence Services Orthopaedic Hospital (500-bedded), Mingalardon. The medical records of patients admitted to specific wards who were prescribed opioid and non-opioid analgesics during the study period were studied.

Approval and permission to conduct research in the hospital were obtained from the hospital's Commandant. Medical records of eligible patients were reviewed to collect data on weekdays and weekends. Data collected included details of analgesic usage (dose, dosage, route, combination with gastrointestinal protective drugs), demographic data, and clinical information. Data were coded and analyzed using Microsoft Excel software. Age, sex distribution, and the proportion of opioid and non-opioid analgesic use were evaluated. Prescribed analgesics were classified, and their volume was transformed into Defined Daily Dose (DDD) using the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification and DDDs according to ATC index. Total DDDs for each analgesic and DDDs per 1000 inhabitants per day were calculated.

Example of Calculation (Diclofenac):

- Total items (tablets) of diclofenac prescribed during the study period = 860 tablets
- Amount of diclofenac per item (tablets) = 50 mg
- Total amount of diclofenac prescribed during the study period = 43,000 mg
- DDD of diclofenac by ATC index with DDDs 2019 = 100 mg
- Number of DDDs = (Number of item used x Amount of drug per item (mg)) / (WHO recommended DDD of drug) = (860 tablets x 50 mg) / (100 mg) = 430 DDDs
- DDDs per 1000 inhabitants per day = (Total consumption in DDDs x 1000) / (Covered inhabitants x period of data collection in days) **OR** (Total no. of dosage unit prescribed x Strength of each dosage unit x 1000) / (DDD x Duration of study x Total sample size)
- DDDs per 1000 inhabitants per day = (860 x 50 x 1000) / (100 x 92 x 450) = 10.3864

Where;

Total no. of dosage unit prescribed	=	860 tablets
Strength of each dosage unit	=	50mg
Total sample size	=	450 patients in the study
Duration of study	=	92 days (for 3 months duration)

The result of 10.3864 DDD/1000 inhabitants per day indicates that approximately 1.04% of the population may have theoretically received a standard dose of diclofenac every day.

3. Results

3.1. Demographic data of the patients in the study who were prescribed with opioid or non-opioid analgesics

Out of total 278 admitted patients to the hospital, 260 patients (94%) were prescribed with opioid and non-opioid analgesics within the study period. Notably, within the study population, 150 patients, constituting 57.69% of the total, fell within the age of 18 to 35 years, while 23 patients, accounting for 8.67% of the total, were situated within the older demographic category of 55 years and above. Furthermore, the distribution of patients across age categories revealed that 29 individuals (11.33%) belonged to the age group below 18 years, and 58 patients (22.31%) were positioned in the 36 to 55-year age range. Over the period of three months, 260 patients were prescribed opioid and non-opioid analgesics. Among them, 203 (81%) were males and 57 (19%) were females. So, males were more admitted than females during the study period.

In trauma ward, 142 patients (54.62%) and in general ward, 33 patients (12.70%) were admitted. In family ward, 56 patients (21.54%) and in officer ward, 29 patients (11.15%) were admitted (Table 1).

In this study, trauma cases such as mine injuries, spinner wound injuries, gunshot wound injuries and road traffic accident cases were the commonest cause for admission to hospital (41.14%) and chronic osteomyelitis was the least indication for analgesic use with 4.62% of the study population. The indications for analgesic use in the study population is described in (Table 2.)

Out of 260 patients, 246 patients were also prescribed with gastro-protective agents. Proton pump inhibitors was the most co-prescribed gastro-protective agent with 141 patients (57.32%) of the study population. H₂ blockers was the second most prescribed in 61 patients (24.80%).

Table 1. Distribution of the admitted patients treated with opioid and non-opioid analgesics in DSOH

Wards of DSOH	No. of admitted patients	Percent (%)
Trauma ward	142	54.62
General ward	33	12.70
Family ward	56	21.53
Officer ward	29	11.15
Total	260	100

Table 2. Indications for opioid and non-opioid analgesics usage in study population

Indications for analgesic usage	Number of patients	Percentage
Trauma		
1. Mines injuries	46	17.70
2. Spinner wound injuries	32	12.31
3. Gunshot wound injuries	18	6.92
4. Road traffic accident	11	4.22
Fracture	35	13.46
Osteoarthritis	33	12.70
Cervical spondylosis	29	11.15
Others (Abscess, swelling)	29	11.15
PID/ low back pain	15	5.77
Chronic Osteomyelitis	12	4.62
Total	260	100

3.2. Drug utilization results of the opioid and non-opioid analgesics usage in the study population

Total utilization of opioid analgesics was 22.5 (2.25%) DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. Oral tramadol tablet usage was the highest with 18 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day and the data was described in (Table 3.).

Total utilization of non-opioid analgesics was 99.74 (9.97%) DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day. Among the non-opioid analgesics, DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day of the aceclofenac was the highest with 35.67 DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day and the whole data is described in (Table 4.).

In this study, combination of analgesics that prescribed to patients were totally 81 (31.15%). Combination of opioid and non-opioid analgesics was 17 (6.53%) and non-opioid with non-opioid combination was 64 (24.62%). Among the combination of analgesics, aceclofenac and paracetamol combination was the most prescribed in patients with 25 (9.62%) followed by diclofenac and paracetamol combination. Non-opioid analgesics alone was the most prescribed in 151 (58.08%) patients (Table 5.).

Tramadol tablets was the most prescribed opioid analgesic in 11 patients (4.23%) and tramadol injection to 7 (2.70%) followed by morphine tablet (2.31%) and morphine injection in 1.54% of patients as described in (Table 6.).

Combination therapy of non-opioid analgesics was mostly prescribed in patients (24.62%). Aceclofenac alone was the most prescribed non-opioid analgesic in patients (15.77%) followed by diclofenac (11.92%), paracetamol (8.08%), meloxicam (6.54%), ibuprofen (5%), etoricoxib (4.23%), celecoxib (3.46%) and ketorolac (3.08%). The use of non-opioid analgesics was described in (Table. 7).

Aceclofenac, diclofenac, paracetamol, tramadol, meloxicam and injection tramadol were included in DU 90%. Drug utilization 90% of analgesics that were prescribed among the patients who admitted to DSOH (500-bedded), Mingalardon was described in (Table 8.).

Table 3. Drug utilization of opioid analgesics by ATC code and DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day in orthopedic wards of DSOH

Drug	ATC code	DDD mg (WHO, 2019)	Total DDDs	DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day
Tramadol tablet	N02AX02	300	102.83	18
Tramadol injection	N02AX02	300	19.33	3.07
Morphine tablet	N02AA01	100	102.83	18
Morphine injection	N02AA01	30	4.03	0.22
Total				22.5

Table 4. Drug utilization of non-opioid analgesics by ATC code and DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day in orthopedic wards of DSOH

Drugs	ATC code	DDD mg (WHO, 2019)	DDDs	DDDs/1000 Inhabitants per day
Aceclofenac	M01AB16	200	410	35.67
Diclofenac	M01AH05	100	235	25.35
Paracetamol	N02BE01	3000	7855	19.22
Meloxicam	M01AC06	15	100.5	13.61
Ibuprofen	M01AC06	1200	27.33	2.15
Etoricoxib	M01AH05	60	16	1.51
Celecoxib	M01AH01	200	28.5	1.20
Ketorolac	M01AB15	30	12.33	1.03
Total				99.74

Table 5. Proportion of usage of opioid and non-opioid analgesics combination and alone

Type of drugs	No. of Patients	Percent (%)
Analgesics combination	81	31.15
Combination of opioid and non-opioid analgesics		
1. Tramadol + aceclofenac	9	3.46
2. Tramadol + paracetamol	8	3.07
Total	17	6.53
Combination of non-opioid with non-opioid		
1. Aceclofenac + paracetamol	25	9.62
2. Diclofenac + paracetamol	12	4.62
3. Meloxicam + paracetamol	11	4.23
4. Celecoxib + aceclofenac	6	2.30
5. Ibuprofen + paracetamol	10	3.85
Total	64	24.62
Opioid alone	28	10.77
Non-opioid alone	151	58.08
Total	260	100

Table 6. Usage of different types of opioid analgesic drugs among the study population

Opioid analgesics	No. of patients	Percentage
Tramadol tablet	11	4.23
Tramadol injection	7	2.70
Morphine tablet	6	2.31
Morphine injection	4	1.54
Total	28	10.77

Table 7. Usage of different types of non-opioid analgesic drugs among the study population

Type of non-opioid analgesics	Number of patients	Percentage
Non- Selective		
Combination therapies	64	24.62
Aceclofenac	41	15.77
Paracetamol	21	8.08
diclofenac	31	11.92
Meloxicam	17	6.54
Ibuprofen	13	5
Ketorolac	8	3.08
Selective		
Etoricoxib	11	4.23
Celecoxib	9	3.46
Total	151	58.08

Table 8. Drug utilization 90% of analgesics that were prescribed among the patients who admitted to DSOH (500-bedded), Mingalardon

Drugs	ATC code	DDD mg	DDDs	DDDs/1000 inhabitants per day	Percentage
Aceclofenac	M01AB16	200	410	35.67	28.37
Diclofenac	M01AH05	100	233	25.35	20.16
Paracetamol	N02BE01	3000	785	19.22	15.29
Tramadol	N02AX02	300	102.83	18	14.32
Meloxicam	M01AC06	15	100.5	17.11	13.61
Tramadol Injection	N02AB03	300	19.33	3.07	2.44
Ibuprofen	M01AE01	1200	27.33	2.15	1.71
Etoricoxib	M01AH05	30	16	1.51	1.21
Morphin tablet	N02AA01	100	8.78	1.22	0.98
Celecoxib	M01AH01	200	28.5	1.20	0.93
Ketorolac	M01AB15	30	12.33	1.03	0.82
Morphin injection	N02AA01	30	4.03	0.22	0.16

4. Discussion

This study conducted at DSOH (500-bedded), Mingalardon reveals significant insights into the patient demographics, prescription patterns, and drug utilization in a specialized medical setting primarily catering to military personnel. The hospital's focus on the healthcare needs of soldiers and their families results in distinct characteristics in patient profiles and medication prescriptions.

The analysis of patient data indicates that a substantial proportion of admissions falls within the age group of young adults, particularly those aged 18-35 years. This trend can be attributed to the military's preference for deploying individuals in this age group due to their suitability for active military operations. Consequently, this age group is at a higher risk of sustaining injuries that require orthopaedic care and hospitalization. Conversely, the number of patients under the age of 18 is relatively low, as military hospitals typically serve soldiers and their families, excluding civilian patients. The study also highlights gender disparities in hospital admissions, with a clear preponderance of male patients. This discrepancy can be attributed to the nature of military service, where males are more frequently exposed to combat situations and, consequently, are at a higher risk of injuries such as mine injuries, gunshot wounds, and other accidents. The male predominance in admissions is consistent with the hospital's mission to treat military-related injuries.

The prescription patterns within the military hospital reveal the use of a combination of opioid and non-opioid analgesics. Notably, non-selective COX inhibitors like aceclofenac and diclofenac are the most commonly prescribed non-opioid analgesics, and proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are often co-prescribed to mitigate the risk of peptic ulcers and gastrointestinal bleeding. The choice of these medications aligns with their effectiveness in managing pain and reducing inflammation.

Opioid analgesics, crucial for managing severe pain, are prevalent in this military hospital. Tramadol, a synthetic opioid with both opioid receptor agonist and norepinephrine-serotonin reuptake inhibition properties, is the most commonly prescribed opioid analgesic. Its frequent use can be attributed to its efficacy in addressing pain associated with war injuries, such as mine injuries and spinner wound injuries.

In another military hospital, the No. (2) Defence Services General Hospital in Naypyitaw, a study on non-opioid analgesic drugs utilization revealed a significantly lower utilization rate of 11.89 DDD/1000 inhabitants per day compared to the current study. Paracetamol was the most frequently prescribed drug in this study, followed by diclofenac, ketorolac, celecoxib, and ibuprofen, as reported in the study by Nyi-Nyi-Aye-Thein et al. in

2014. These variations in non-opioid analgesic utilization among different military hospitals may be attributed to differences in hospital settings and the types of patients admitted (9).

Similarly, drug utilization patterns concerning analgesics in civilian hospitals vary depending on the specific hospitals and patient populations. For instance, a study conducted by Yamin et al. in 2019, assessing the utilization, availability, and quality of pain control in surgical patients within general surgical wards of Thingangyun Sanpya General Hospital and Yangon General Hospital, reported a total analgesic usage rate of 11.04% DDD/1000 inhabitants per day. In this study, diclofenac emerged as the most commonly prescribed analgesic, followed by tramadol, ketorolac, paracetamol, and fentanyl, respectively (10).

Furthermore, another study conducted by Pyae-Phyo in 2019 focused on the drug utilization patterns of opioid analgesics among patients with cancer pain attending the Radiation Oncology and Medical Oncology Departments of Yangon General Hospital. The study found a considerably higher total utilization rate of opioid analgesics at 109.3594 DDD/1000 inhabitants per day. Oral tramadol tablets were the most frequently prescribed opioid, followed by oral codeine, oral morphine tablets, oral morphine syrup, and parenteral tramadol injections (11).

Comparative analyses with the forementioned studies (5,9,10,11) in civilian and military settings reveal variations in drug utilization patterns. In civilian hospitals, analgesic prescription trends can differ significantly depending on patient demographics, nature of illnesses, and the hospital's mission. For instance, the military hospital studied here sees a higher utilization of opioid analgesics, likely due to the specific needs of military personnel.

The study underscores the importance of tailored healthcare provision in specialized settings like military hospitals. Monitoring drug consumption, analyzing prescription patterns, and ensuring the rational use of analgesics are essential aspects of healthcare delivery. The findings can inform procurement decisions, policy formulation, and optimization of healthcare services.

5. Conclusion

In summary, this study sheds light on the unique patient demographics and prescription patterns within a military hospital. It highlights the distinctive characteristics of healthcare provision for soldiers and their families, including the higher utilization of opioid analgesics for combat-related injuries. The study's insights contribute to a better understanding of healthcare practices in specialized medical settings and emphasize the importance of rational drug use and patient-centric care.

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